

SELECTION OF FIBRACONTE COMPOSITION AND STUDY OF PROPERTIES

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Abstract: For the development of the production of fiber concrete and concrete products based on waste, requirements are set for the efficiency and quality of construction work. In order to successfully implement these, it is necessary to achieve a reduction in total energy expenditure in materials and constructions, development of production, raw materials, construction cost and labor, reduction of the weight of buildings and structures, repair and their construction and operation.

Key words: Basalt stone, basalt fiber, basalt reinforcement, fiber concrete.

Today, the need to obtain high-strength concrete for the construction of modern skyscrapers is increasing, in this place the demand for fiber concrete is particularly important. Studying its composition and properties is one of the most important areas. studied.

The joint venture in the form of a limited liability company "Mega invest industrial" acts as the main supplier of construction materials for these structures.

The enterprise, which started operating in December 2017, processes basalt stone and produces basalt fiber and fittings. Currently, the first and second phases of the project have been launched. For this purpose, 11 million dollars of investment from the British company "Leigh Borrier" and 26 million dollars of loan from the National Bank of Uzbekistan were directed. Know-how technologies from countries such as Germany, France, Italy, Russia, and Turkey have been installed. 225 people are employed.

In 2018, a thousand tons of basalt fittings and tiles were produced here. It is planned to start the third stage in the near future. When the enterprise works at full capacity, 4 thousand tons of basalt fiber and 4 thousand 800 tons of fittings are produced in one year.

The advantage of basalt reinforcement is that it is 8 times lighter than metal reinforcement, 3 times stronger, and 30 percent cheaper. In addition, it does not rust, does not conduct electricity, does not lose its properties for up to 100 years. This enterprise is significant in that it is the only one in Central Asia and the second in the CIS countries.

1,5 sm li bazalt tolali fibra beton sinash natijalari							
№	Fiber diameter μm	Fiber length mm	D concrete	d metal	percentage	Press index Rc	average
1	17	15	11	3,5	0	80,3	91,7
2	17	15	10	4		100	
3	17	15	10	4		95	
1	17	15	10	4	1	122	114
2	17	15	9,5	3,5		120	
3	17	15	11,5	4,5		100	
1	17	15	9	3	2	112	107,3
2	17	15	11	3		100	
3	17	15	10	3,1		110	
1	17	15	10	4	3	124	124,6
2	17	15	10	4		125	
3	17	15	8	4		125	
1	17	15	9	4	4	115	120
2	17	15	10	3		125	
3	17	15	9	3		120	

1 cm basalt fiber concrete test results

№	Fiber diameter µm	Fiber length mm	D concrete	d metal	percentage	Press index Rc	average
1	17	10	11	3,5	0	80,3	91,7
2	17	10	10	4		100	
3	17	10	10	4		95	
1	17	10	8	3,5	1	122	124,3
2	17	10	9,5	3,5		125	
3	17	10	11	3		126	
1	17	10	9	3,5	2	125	125,3
2	17	10	9,5	3,5		125	
3	17	10	8,5	3,5		126	
1	17	10	8	3,5	3	128	128
2	17	10	8,5	3		127	

3	17	10	9,5	3,5		129	
1	17	10	9,5	3,8	4	126	125
2	17	10	10	3		125	
3	17	10	9	3		124	

0,5 cm basalt fiber concrete test results							
№	Fiber diameter μm	Fiber length mm	D concrete	d metal	percentage	Presss index Rc	average
1	17	5	11	3,5	0	80,3	91,7
2	17	5	10	4		100	
3	17	5	10	4		95	
1	17	5	10,5	4	1	100	105
2	17	5	9	3,5		100	
3	17	5	12	3		115	
1	17	5	9,5	4	2	125	122,3
2	17	5	10	3		114	
3	17	5	9	3,5		128	
1	17	5	9	4	3	140	139,6
2	17	5	8,8	3,8		137	
3	17	5	8	4		142	
1	17	5	8	3,5	4	126	126
2	17	5	9	3,5		125	
3	17	5	9	3,5		127	

Effective use of the opportunities created for small business and private business entities in 2021, which was completed based on the proposals and recommendations and tasks given by the President during his visit to the region in March last year, became a factor of ensuring high rates of economic growth.

Based on the selection of the composition of fiber concrete based on the

waste from the production of basalt reinforcement, which we have selected above, and as a result of studying its properties, we can know from the results obtained on this material that it is efficient to use it in the construction industry. Because the strength of the ordinary heavy concrete sample increased by 40% as a result of adding 5 mm fiber in the amount of 3%, it is possible to increase the strength of this 10,000 kg concrete to 14,000 kg.

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